

Optimized proportional-integral controller for a photovoltaic-virtual synchronous generator system

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ABSTRACT

Due to the lack of a physical rotating rotor, the photovoltaic generators (PVG) have no inertia. Therefore, replacing traditional synchronous generators (SG), (source of inertia), with PVG will reduce the inertia of overall power systems. A reduced inertia and damping feature will frequently cause instability issues due to high rate of change of frequency (RoCoF), and less stringent voltage at the nearby point of common coupling (PCC). In this paper, the concept of virtual synchronous generators (VSG) is adopted in to couple the source with the grid frequency in order to provide virtual inertia. This is created by using energy storage for short time, direct current (DC) to alternating current (AC) converter, and a suitable control mechanism. In implementing VSG, the important aspects to focus on are reducing the fluctuation of DC-link voltage, stabilize the frequency and voltage, and power flow. So, the particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithm was used to adjust the parameters of proportional integral (PI) controller by reducing the error of the current controller and voltage regulator in the VSG controller. The simulation results illustrate the advantages of the PI tuning using PSO, where the overshoot is decreased by 68.9% and the settling time is decreased by 34% due to load fluctuations.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The frequency of a power system is an essential criterion for evaluating its power surplus and deficit [1]. In the case of a disturbance, traditional synchronous generators (SGs) will use the kinetic energy stored in their rotational inertia to balance the power grid's potential energy variation. Therefore, the system will return to stability after disturbances [2]. The photovoltaic (PV) system is a static source, which does not have any rotating parts. In addition, PV systems do not have the same dynamic features as traditional SG, due to a lack of inverter inertia and damping [3]. So, a large-scale PV power plant will decrease the inertia of all power systems and weaken the system's primary frequency response ability [4]. Most renewable energy sources (RESs) are connected to the grid using power inverters as grid following units [5]. The converter injects the active power into the grid after synchronization with the grid voltage. Therefore, the renewable energy supply stops feeding power into the grid after any disturbance. As a result, concerns about stability arise due to increased renewable energy penetration [6].

Due to the above reasons, virtual synchronous generator (VSG) technology was implemented into the PV market to enable PV grid-connected inverters to work similarly to SGs [7]. This control method helps control the inverters in a weak grid since it blends the fast response of the inverter with its SG's static and

In the above system, a BESS is connected to a solar power plant's DC-link, and its function is to inject (discharging mode) or absorb (charging mode) the power to the system for a short time during the disturbance. The charging and discharging method use a bi-directional buck-boost converter connected to BESS that adjusts the input current of BESS. Thus, a BESS can be constructed to compensate for the power intermittence of a PV system during normal conditions such as solar irradiance variability produced by passing clouds. In contrast, the solar plant still operates at its maximal power point tracking (MPPT) mode to achieve the highest power efficiency possible.

Measured three-phase voltages and currents from the three-phase (abc) system's load bus are converted to dq0 rotating reference frame using Park's transformation. In addition, the active and reactive power is measured, and the results are used as input signals to the active power-frequency control (P-f) and reactive power-voltage control (Q-V) blocks. Droop controllers have been used to provide frequency and voltage stability. The P-f droop controller calculates the phase angle and the frequency of the VSG, and the Q-V droop controller calculates the reference voltage. The synthesis algorithm will then use the phase angle and frequency to determine the reference current for current control blocks. The current controller calculates the three-phase reference voltage for the pulse width modulation (PWM).

3. SYSTEM MODELING

3.1. Modeling of photovoltaic array

The main constituents of PV arrays are photovoltaic cells. Its function is to transform solar energy into electricity when exposed to light [17]. PV includes short circuit current (I_{sc}), open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), maximum voltage (V_{MPP}), and maximum current (I_{MPP}). The I-V and P-V curves are shaped by these parameters. A single diode and a two-diode model are used to simulate a PV two diodes are more accurate, but more variables are required to make the model more complex [17]. A simplified single diode PV module current is represented by (1) [18].

$$I_{PV} = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{qV_{PV}}{KTAN_s}} - 1 \right), \quad (1)$$

Where I_{PV} and V_{PV} are the PV output current and voltage, respectively, I_{ph} is the current produced from photon bombardment on the solar cell surface, I_0 is dark current of saturation, usually about 10^{-12} A/cm², N_s is the number of modules connected in series, q is the electron charge, K is the Boltzmann constant, T is the module temperature, and A is the diode ideality constant.

3.2. Battery energy storage system (BESS)

Characteristics of the battery charging and discharging method for short or long periods are described in [19], [20]. There are many models for BESS design, and some of these types are not used in electrical design because the time constant is higher than the electrical time constant. Figure 2 shows the use of the voltage source resistance model to simplify the electrochemical calculations.

Figure 2. Equivalent circuit of BESS

From the Figure 2, E_{Bat} is the battery's electromotive force (E.M.F), R represents the battery's internal resistance in the charging state (R_{ch}) and discharging states (R_{dis}), which both contribute to the energy loss inside the battery during charging and discharging, i_{Bat} is the charging and discharging current where the positive value of i_{Bat} represents the charging current and the negative value the discharging current and V_{Bat} represents the terminal voltage of the battery. In this model, E_{Bat} and electric parameters R_{ch} and R_{dis} , all dependent on SOC and the operating temperature (T_{emp}) of the battery as shown in (2) [21].

$$V_{Bat}(SOC, T_{emp}) = E_{Bat}(SOC, T_{emp}) + i_{Bat} R(SOC, T_{emp}) \quad (2)$$

3.3. Bi-directional direct current/direct current converter design

Figure 3 (a) shows the structure of a bi-directional DC/DC converter, which controls the charging and discharging of BESS. The design of the DC/DC bi-directional converter depends on boosting topology, this meaning that the voltage of BESS is always lower than the DC-link voltage. To achieve the two-way power conversion [22]. Both of the DC/DC converter switches, S_1 and S_2 , must be coordinated by a control system, where the BESS current is regulated by the inner current loop to track the given command i_{Bat}^* . Figure 3 (b) shows this control system. The outer voltage loop controls the DC-link voltage and generates a reference signal for the inner loop i_{Bat}^* [23].

Figure 3. Control system of BESS where (a) structure and (b) block diagram

3.4. Droop control of virtual synchronous generators (VSG)

The droop control is a control method that emulates the external characteristics of the SG output to control the inverter and distribute the inverter load power evenly [24]. The system voltage is determined by decoupling the droop characteristic curve between reactive power and voltage (Q-V), and active power and frequency (P-f). The droop controller will give the reference value of the voltage amplitude and frequency during the control process. In a DG system, P-f and Q-V droop controls are widely used to control active, and reactive power [11], [12], [24]. Frequency control must have a drooping characteristic with respect to the generator output for a power generator's stability, as shown in Figure 4 (a).

The power droop characteristic can be expressed by (3) [5], [13].

$$f_r = f_n + k_p (P_n - P_r) \tag{3}$$

Where f_r is reference grid frequency, f_n is nominal frequency, P_r and P_n are a reference and nominal active power respectively, and k_p is the P-f droop coefficient.

The terminal voltage of power generators is directly related to the reactive power supplied by the generator, and it has a drooping feature, as seen in Figure 4 (b). This Q-V droop characteristic is expressed by the following (4) [12].

$$V_r = V_n + k_v (Q_n - Q_r), \tag{4}$$

Where k_v is reactive droop coefficients, V_r is the output voltage amplitude when the inverter output reactive power (Q_r) is zero.

Figure 4. Droop characteristics for a DG system to (a) P-f droop control and (b) Q-V droop control

4. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF VIRTUAL SYNCHRONOUS GENERATORS

The VSG control contains two links, active and reactive power control. VSG's active power control regulates the frequency, matches the speed control system in SG, and adds inertia and damping to the active power control. The voltage amplitude is adjusted using reactive power control [25], like the excitation system in SG, making the inverter's external properties identical to those of a conventional SG, which will have rotational inertia to maintain grid smooth operation [13]. The second-order model of SG [14], [15] was used in this work, which includes the stator voltage equation and the rotor mechanical equation, respectively, as shown in (5) and (6).

$$E = V + I (R_a + j X_S), \quad (5)$$

$$J \frac{dw_m}{dt} = T_m - T_e, \quad (6)$$

Where E is excitation voltage, V is armature voltage, I is armature current, R_a is armature resistance, X_S is synchronous reactance, J is a moment of inertia, w_m is the mechanical angular velocity, T_m , and T_e are mechanical and electrical torque. The rotor motion equation can be derived from (6) by using the synchronous rotation axis as the reference axis and using the relationship between electrical and mechanical angular velocity $w = p w_m$ and the number of pole pairs ($p = 1$).

$$J \frac{d(w-w_n)}{dt} = \frac{1}{w} (P_m - P_e), \quad (7)$$

Where w is the electric angular velocity, w_n is the synchronous electrical angular velocity, P_m and P_e are mechanical and electromagnetic power, respectively. The control algorithm model of the VSG is developed using (5) and (7).

5. PARTICLE SWARM OPTIMIZATION (PSO) TECHNIQUE

PSO is an ideal optimization approach that benefits from simplicity in design, robustness, and global convergence over the other optimization methods [26]. In this article, the fortunate K_p and K_i parameters were selected to search for the optimal values to make the error as small or zero as possible. This feature can control algorithm convergence and get the optimal value of the objective function [27]. The PI controller is generally a feedback control system based on a linear system equation for load conditions. The main reasons for selecting the PI controller to regulate an inverter system are good control performance, easy design, and high reliability.

Most voltage and current controllers in the AC system used PI controller to control in the DC-link voltage and the grid current. The injected power to the grid is properly controlled and the DC-link voltage of the inverter is stable [17], [28]. The PSO algorithm optimization technique is used to provide the best optimal value of K_p and K_i to reduce overshoot, transient response, and to obtain low steady-state error related to loading change. The inverter control model proposed with the PSO technique is illustrated in Figure 1. A PSO technique is implemented to design the PI controller parameters optimally to reduce the error for the current controller and voltage regulator. Moreover, compared to the other algorithms, which need to use a trial-and-error method, this required a long time through implementation. On the other hand, PSO required a short time to find the optimal values of PI parameters and simple implementation [27].

The main PSO algorithms depend on two factors velocity and position. This factor is updated by applying (8), (9) [29].

$$V_i^{n+1} = \omega V_i^n + C_1 r_1 (P_i^n - X_i^n) + C_2 r_2 (P_g^n - X_i^n), \quad (8)$$

$$X_i^{n+1} = X_i^n + V_i^{n+1}, \quad (9)$$

Where ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4 \dots m$), n is no. of iterations, ω is weight coefficient, C_1 and C_2 are the social and cognitive rate, respectively, and r_1 and r_2 are random intervals (0, 1). The fitness function of the system is described in (10).

$$\min F(x) = c_1 \int_0^{T_{max}} e(t)^2 dt + c_2 (\max(e^{-1})) \quad (10)$$

Where T_{max} is max. time, e is the error, c_1 and c_2 are wight coefficients. In the beginning, the PSO algorithm randomly starts to calculate fitness and achieve the best value for each parameter in the entire swarm. MATLAB code was used to implement the proposed PSO algorithm. The optimization steps of the PSO algorithm are described in the flowchart shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. The advanced PSO algorithm flowchart for the VSG control system

6. RESULT

A 250 kW PV is connected to the grid during normal operation. The PV mainly provides the loads in the system. If the PV cannot provide all the loads, the power shortage is supplied by the grid. The parameters of the proposed VSG used for the simulation are given in Table 1. If a significant system disturbance occurs, the system frequency quickly deviates from its nominal value, and the rate of change of frequency (RoCoF) will be very high over the maximum limits, leads to instability and system collapse. Therefore, VSG is used to maintain system stability during disturbances.

Table 1. Simulation parameters

Parameters	Values	Parameters	Values
Rated power	250 kW	Virtual inertia, J	10 kg·m ²
Grid voltage (L-L)	400 V	Filter capacitor C_f	40 μF
Grid frequency	50 Hz	Filter inductor L_f	0.815 mH
DC voltage	800 V	Bidirectional resistance R	0.05 Ω
Switching frequency	10 kHz	Bidirectional inductor L	0.3 mH

PSO is used to tuning the parameters of the PI controller for VSG to improves the power quality of VSG connected to the grid and compared the results with conventional VSG. The trial-and-error method by using MATLAB/Simulink was used to implement the initial value to the VSG system's PI controller. The PSO algorithm code was then simulated. The test results are presented for the following case:

6.1. Case 1: comparisons of different control methods

In this case, a PV system connected to the grid is considered. Then a VSG model is designed to study its characteristic in the modification of its output and moment of inertia according to load changes. Finally, a PSO technic is used to improve the parameters of VSG. The integrated system model connected to the load in the grid-connected mode is built-in MATLAB/Simulink. To analyze the voltage and frequency oscillations, a sudden load change is considered. A local load of 250 kW is connected to the PV initially. The

solar radiation for the PV system is 1000 W/m^2 and the solar temperature is 25° . At $t = 1 \text{ sec}$, the load is suddenly increased by 50 kW (20%), and at $t = 2 \text{ sec}$ the load decreased by 50 kW .

Figure 6 shows the DC link voltage, RMS value of PCC voltage, and system frequency of the PV without VSG, PV with VSG, and VSG-PSO. It can be seen from Figure 6 (a) that the system frequency for the PV without VSG changes rapidly with the sudden change of the load, and the fluctuation is very steep. also, the RoCoF is outside the permissible limits as shown in Figure 6 (b), and there is a drop in the PCC voltage when the load increase as shown Figure 6 (c). Also, the DC-link voltage is not constant and changes dramatically with a sudden change in the load, as shown in Figure 6 (d). So, the small oscillations in frequency and voltage may adversely affect the system stability.

When VSG connected the fluctuation in the system's frequency and RoCoF becomes very small within the permissible limits, and the change in the frequency and RoCoF will be slowly and more gradually as shown in Figures 6 (a) and 6 (b) respectively. This is due to the energy injected by BES when the load increases. And when the load decreases, the BES will absorb power by charging itself for a short time until the grid provides the power to the load or receives the excess power from the PV. The battery balances the generated power with the load power which makes the frequency always stable as shown in Figure 7. And the presence of the battery will make the DC-link voltage constant as shown in Figure 6 (d), so the drop in the load voltage will be very small as shown in Figure 6 (c).

Figure 6. Frequency response and voltage of the system with under a sudden change in load: without VSG, with VSG and VSG-PSO (a) frequency response, (b) RoCoF, (c) RMS load voltage, and (d) DC-link voltage

Figures 6 (a) and 6 (b) shows a significant reduction in frequency oscillation RoCoF due to the use of PSO. The optimized parameters using PSO make the system respond faster in providing the required power during a sudden change of load and reduce the peak overshoot (O.S.) and settling time (Ts). As in the conventional VSG, the drop in load voltage is minimal and the DC-link voltage is constant, during an increase in the load, as shown in Figures 6 (c) and 6 (d), respectively. It is clear from Figures 6 (a) and 6 (b) that the existence of VSG with and without PSO has helped to decrease the amplitude of the frequency deviation and the RoCoF to the permissible limits, also the frequency returns to the study state in a short time. The maximum overshoot, settling time, RoCoF, and drop voltage with a step-change in load is given in Table 2.

Figure 7. Output power of BESS for the sudden change in load in VSG

Table 2. Effect of VSG on frequency and voltage response with step load change

	Peak overshoot (Hz)		Settling time (sec)		RoCoF (Hz/s)		Drop voltage (V)
	Load increase	Load decrease	Load increase	Load decrease	Load increase	Load decrease	Load increase
Without VSG	0.54	0.56	0.512	0.498	1.09	1.11	5
With VSG	0.074	0.073	0.229	0.221	0.316	0.319	0.85
VSG-PSO	0.023	0.025	0.141	0.134	0.24	0.25	0.7

6.2. Case 2: transient analysis of grid-connected photovoltaic system with step change in irradiance

In this case, PV model irradiance was changed from a constant of 1000 W/m² to 500 W/m² at t = 1.5 s. The system load was kept constant at 250 kW. The frequency variations of the system are shown in Figure 8 (a). While using VSG control, the system performance is tested for irradiance changes from 1000 W/m² to 500 W/m² at t=1.5 s. The minimum frequency deviation in the grid-connected PV system was reduced from 49.132 Hz to 49.82 Hz. Using PSO, the frequency variation decreased to 49.923 Hz, which was within the normal operating range of 0.2 Hz, as shown in Figure 8 (a). And the RoCoF also decrease to allowable limits when using VSG with and without PSO as shown in Figure 8 (b). RoCoF, peck overshoot, and settling time of the frequency response with change in the irradiance are listed in Table 3. And as the inertia increases, the reduction in the frequency will increase. This reduction should prevent frequency relays from being tripped unnecessarily. Figure 9 depicts the power injected and the power absorbed by BESS to reduce frequency deviation caused by a change in irradiance.

Figure 8. Various simulation scenarios due to irradiance change (without VSG, conventional VSG and VSG based PSO) (a) frequency response and (b) RoCoF response

Table 3. Effect of VSG on frequency response with change in irradiance

	Peak overshoot (Hz)	Settling time (sec)	RoCoF
Without VSG	0.868	0.739	1.52
With VSG	0.192	0.611	0.6
VSG-PSO	0.0652	0.289	0.41

Figure 9. The output power of BESS due to a change in irradiance

In this paper, the PSO algorithm is implemented under various disturbances for the optimum tuning of PI factors used in the VSG. The optimization process requires a period to retune the PI controllers. The values of estimated time delay for each scenario are listed in Tables 4 and 5 for different irradiances. This delay time used then to implementation the suggested online PSO algorithm to improve power system quality.

Table 4. Estimation of time delay for online tuning PI controllers at full irradiance

Load (kW)	Six-Dimensional Particles of PI Controllers						Time Delay (sec)
	K_{pd}	K_{id}	K_{pq}	K_{iq}	K_{pv}	K_{iv}	
250	100	1539.2	24.8	4807.9	0.001	1000	14.4
200	100	1233	12.9	5000	0.0012	624	7.20
150	52.9	3433.5	100	625	0.0011	132.3	4.00
100	22.2	5000	81.3	2320.5	0.0014	272.3	3.20
Average Time (sec)							7.20

Table 5. Estimation of time delay for online self-tuning of VSG-PI controllers at half irradiance

Load (kW)	Six-Dimensional Particles of PI Controllers						Time Delay (sec)
	K_{pd}	K_{id}	K_{pq}	K_{iq}	K_{pv}	K_{iv}	
100	112.3	11.9	4196.7	0.001	50	9.00	100
100	4566	9.2	5000	0.0012	716	8.00	100
95.2	2483.4	29.7	122.6	0.0011	995	4.00	95.2
46.32	489.93	100	4532	0.0013	460	4.00	46.32
Average Time (sec)							6.25

7. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes using VSG control for a PV system to emulate the behavior of a real SG. This study uses PV-VSG control and B.E. to enable virtual inertia for the power systems. In addition, the PSO technique is used to obtain optimal tuning of PI controller parameters (K_p , K_i) of the VSG controller. In this manner, grid frequency ancillary services are provided by the PVG as the grid codes require. In other words, when the power system's frequency falls under allowable limits during the sudden load change and reduction in irradiance, the proposed system counters the situation by supplying available energy. Simulation tests showed that VSG with PSO technique could reduce the frequency overshoot and reduce the time (T_s) required for the frequency to return to its steady state. In the case of VSG without PSO, the frequency is still acceptable when a disturbance occurs. The results also showed that VSG with and without PSO technique maintains DC-link voltage at nominal value and significantly reduces the drop in the load voltage. The proposed future work is to use online optimization using the delay time which was found in this work with different types of disturbance.

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